

FORTY-FIFTH ANNUAL SYMPOSIUM ON FREQUENCY CONTROL

DETERMINATION OF THE LIMITING FACTORS IN THE ABSOLUTE PHASE NOISE OF AN L-BAND DIELECTRIC RESONATOR OSCILLATOR

M. Mizan, R.C. McGowan, T. Lukaszek, and A. Ballato

US ARMY LABCOM, Electronics Tech & Devices Lab, Ft. Monmouth, NJ

Abstract

After developing and evaluating a state-of-the-art two-stage L-Band Dielectric Resonator Oscillator (DRO), more detailed information about the noise contributions from the individual components needed to be determined. Determination of the noise limiting element in an oscillator is vital to any attempted redesign of the oscillator to reduce its absolute phase noise. In an attempt to understand better the noise performance of our two-stage DRO, a single-stage DRO was constructed for comparison. The results of this investigation are presented in the paper.

Introduction

In any analysis of the predominant noise source in an oscillator, it is important to understand which element is expected to control the noise spectrum in a particular frequency regime and what type of power spectral density is anticipated. Typically, in a well-designed oscillator, at large offset frequencies from the carrier, the noise is limited by the loop amplifier and any of the peripheral circuitry external to the oscillator loop. This region is usually characterized by a f^0 power spectral density. For offset frequencies below this portion of the spectrum, there typically is a region of $1/f$ power spectral density which is also generated by the loop amplifier and peripheral circuitry and appears as a 10 dB/decade slope in the phase noise plot of the oscillator. At offset frequencies less than the resonator half bandwidth, a $1/f^3$ spectral density is observed. The source of this noise is two-fold. First, the conversion of $1/f$ and white phase fluctuations in the loop amplifier circuitry will produce a $1/f^3$ spectral density within the resonator half bandwidth. Another possible source of $1/f^3$ noise is short-term $1/f$ frequency fluctuations of the resonator within its

half bandwidth [1]. From this brief discussion it becomes apparent that the performance of the individual components with their $1/f^3$ power spectral density resulting in a 30 dB/decade slope in the half bandwidth of the resonator is critical for the overall performance of an oscillator.

The tool most commonly used for evaluating the noise performance of components in a system is the residual phase noise measurement. This technique allows the investigator to measure the noise added to a signal after it has been processed by any two-port network. Noise added to a signal is the sum of additive and multiplicative noise and has both amplitude and phase modulated components [2]. Using this measurement technique, the actual noise performance of the dielectric resonator and L-Band BJT amplifier can be verified.

Oscillator Design & Temperature Performance

Our discussion will begin with a brief analysis of the design and temperature performance of the one- and two-stage DROs. One can determine from figure 1 that the oscillator is based on a parallel feedback configuration. The amplifier was designed by using S parameters and selecting appropriate input and output matching networks [3]. The resonant cavity structure is shown in figure 2. From the top view of the cavity, one can see that the dielectric resonator is positioned in the center of the cylindrical cavity which corresponds to one-quarter wavelength from the open-circuited end of the 50 ohm microstrip line. This configuration has two advantages. First, by positioning the dielectric resonator one-quarter wavelength away from the open-circuited end of the microstrip line one ensures maximum coupling of the H field into the dielectric resonator. Secondly, by positioning the dielectric resonator in the center of the metallic cavity, the losses due to H field interaction with the walls of the cavity can be minimized.

Once the gain of the one- or two-stage amplifier is measured, the height of the low-loss, low dielectric constant spacer can be determined because the height of the spacer is directly proportional to the insertion loss of the dielectric resonator. The height of the dielectric spacer is selected so that a 2-3 dB loop gain margin is maintained to insure operation over a wide range of temperature and biasing conditions. In the case of the resonator for the two-stage amplifier, figure 3, the insertion loss at the center frequency for the entire resonant structure was 23.5 dB. Given that the gain of the amplifier is 27 dB, there is an excess loop gain of 3.5 dB. Similarly for the single-stage amplifier, the dielectric spacer was chosen to produce an insertion loss of 13 dB in the resonator as seen in figure 4. This provides 2 dB of excess loop gain where the single-stage amplifier has 15 dB of gain.

The loaded quality factor, Q , of the resonator, which is defined as the center frequency divided by the 3 dB bandwidth of the decoupled resonator, can also be measured with the network analyzer. Figure 5 shows the 3 dB bandwidth of the 2 stage resonator as 102 kHz, which corresponds to a loaded Q of 20,500. The results of this two-port measurement for the single-stage resonator shown in figure 6 yielded a 3 dB bandwidth of 165 kHz, which corresponds to a loaded Q of 12,500.

The temperature performance of the two oscillators was examined for completeness. Figures 7 and 8 display the center frequency stability as a function of temperature for the two- and one-stage DROs, respectively. Although very similar, the frequency stability of the single-stage DRO was slightly better with a 100 ppm change over the 100K temperature differential from +55°C to -45°C compared to the 130 ppm change for the two-stage oscillator over the same temperature range. The RF power output response for the two DROs was very different. The two-stage DRO had a constant power output with less than a 1 dBm change in output power over the 100K temperature differential from +55°C to -45°C as seen in figure 9. While the single-stage DRO varied 10 dBm over the same temperature range as seen in figure 10.

Residual and Absolute Phase Noise Performance

After measuring the absolute phase noise of the two-stage oscillator, the question was posed: could the oscillator be improved? This question can be

resolved by performing residual phase noise measurements on the 2-stage amplifier and dielectric resonator. However, the data obtained on the two-stage L-Band bipolar junction transistor (BJT) amplifier and the 2 GHz dielectric resonator were inconclusive because both components gave the system floor as their residual phase noise. Therefore, it was decided to build and evaluate a single-stage L-Band DRO based on the two-stage design to determine if the amplifier was the limiting factor in the two-stage DRO and provide more insight into the overall performance of the oscillator.

One of the primary problems in making residual phase noise measurements is inadequate dynamic range of the system. Enhancement of the system's dynamic range or equivalently the system noise floor was achieved by building a half-watt reflection-type DRO. The block diagram of the residual phase noise test setup is shown in figure 11. The noise floor acquired at 2 GHz using the reflection-type 0.5 watt DRO is given in figure 12. Using this high power oscillator as the frequency source in the test setup, the residual noise of the single-stage BJT amplifier was measured and the results of this test are shown in figure 13. Again the amplifier noise measurement is inconclusive because the data is essentially the same as the system noise floor.

When the 0.5 watt reflection-type DRO was used to make the residual noise measurement on the dielectric resonator it was determined that the frequency instability of the source made it impossible to perform the measurement on such a high Q , narrow bandwidth structure. Therefore, the reflection-type oscillator was replaced with an HP 8662A frequency synthesizer and a doubler to provide a stable source for the resonator. The system floor using this source is shown in figure 14. It should be noted that the system floor is only shown out to 10 kHz because after this point the source noise begins to decorrelate as the offset carrier frequency nears the 3 dB bandwidth of the resonator, making the data invalid. Figure 15 shows the residual noise measurement of the dielectric resonator. Again we see that the resonator's residual phase noise is essentially the same as the system noise floor; therefore the data are inconclusive.

The only conclusive data we obtained that indicated that the amplifier might be the primary noise contributor came from the absolute phase noise data. The absolute phase noise measurement test set up seen in figure 16 was used

for both the 1- and 2-stage DROs. The measurement was made by locking the 155 MHz difference frequency signal, derived by downconverting the test DRO with a low noise High-overtone Bulk Acoustic Resonator (HBAR) oscillator, to a Hewlett Packard (HP) 8662A frequency synthesizer driven by an external 10 MHz VCXO. Figure 17 shows the absolute phase noise data for the two-stage DRO and Figure 18 shows the data for the single-stage DRO. In a direct comparison the higher Q two-stage DRO is approximately 5 to 7 dBc/Hz better than the lower Q single-stage DRO.

Conclusions and Future Work

First, it should be noted that the measured data clearly demonstrate the low phase noise capability and excellent frequency stability of the two-stage, 2 GHz DRO. Residual and absolute phase noise measurements were performed in an attempt to determine the noise limiting element of this state-of-the-art 2 GHz DRO [4]. The residual phase noise measurements for the components of the single- and two-stage DROs were inconclusive because they were virtually indistinguishable from the system noise floor. A comparison of the absolute phase noise performance of the two oscillators did provide some insight into the noise performance of the two-stage oscillator. The 5-7 dBc/Hz improvement in the absolute phase noise of the two-stage DRO is in agreement with Leeson's model for an oscillator whose noise is limited by the amplifier. Leeson's model predicts a 6 dBc/Hz improvement in the absolute phase noise of an oscillator if the oscillator is amplifier limited and the loaded Q is increased by a factor of two. This result agrees with our measured data. Our data predict approximately a 4.2 dBc/Hz improvement in the absolute phase noise of the two-stage oscillator for its 1.63 Q enhancement over the single-stage DRO. The source of the 1-3 dBc/Hz difference between the calculated and the measured data is being investigated.

In the near future we hope to build a high power BJT amplifier to boost the signal output from our stable 2 GHz DRO, so that we can improve the system floor of the residual phase noise measurement test set. By doing this, we hope conclusively to determine the noise contribution of the amplifier and the entire resonant structure.

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to thank Elio Mariani for the technical assistance and encouragement that he offered

throughout our work. We would also like to thank John Ondria for the guidance he provided with our phase noise measurements while he was at Fort Monmouth.

REFERENCES

- [1] G.S. Curtis, "The Relationship between Resonator & Oscillator Noise and Resonator Noise Measurement Techniques", Proceedings of the 41st Annual Symposium on Frequency Control 1987, pp. 420-428, IEEE Catalog No. 87ch2427-3.
- [2] T.R. Faulkner, "Residual Phase Noise Measurement", Microwave Journal, 1989 State of the Art Reference, pp. 135-143.
- [3] Guillermo Gonzalez, Microwave Transistor Amplifier Analysis and Design, Prentice Hall, 1984.
- [4] M.J. Loboda, T.E. Parker, G.K. Montress, "Frequency Stability of L-Band, Two-Port Dielectric Resonator Oscillator", IEEE Transactions on MTT, Vol. MTT35, No. 12, December 1987, pp. 1334-1339.

Figure 1 2 GHz Dielectric Resonator Oscillator Block Diagram

Top View (Lid Removed)

Cross-Sectional View

- | | |
|--------------------------|-------------------------------|
| 1 Metal Cylinder | 4 Low-loss, Dielectric Spacer |
| 2 50-ohm Microstrip Line | 5 Metal Lid |
| 3 Dielectric Resonator | 6 Metal Tuning Screw |

Figure 2 Structure of Resonant Cavity

Figure 3 Center Frequency and Insertion Loss Data for Resonator Used with Two-Stage Amplifier

Figure 4 Center Frequency and Insertion Loss Data for Resonator Used with Single-Stage Amplifier

Figure 5 Loaded Q Data for Resonator Used with Two-Stage Amplifier

Figure 6 Loaded Q Data for Resonator Used with Single-Stage Amplifier

Figure 7 Center Frequency vs Temperature for Two-Stage DRO

Figure 10 Power Output vs Temperature for Single-Stage DRO

Figure 8 Center Frequency vs Temperature for Single-Stage DRO

FIGURE 11 RESIDUAL PHASE NOISE MEASUREMENT TEST SETUP WITH SINGLE-SIDED SPURIOUS CALIBRATION

Figure 9 Power Output vs Temperature for Two-Stage DRO

Figure 12 Noise Floor at 2 GHz Using 0.5 W Reflection-Type DRO

Figure 13 Residual Phase Noise of BJT Amplifier

HBAR: High Overtone Bulk Acoustic Resonator developed by Westinghouse for US Army, LACOM ETDL

Figure 16 Absolute Phase Noise Measurement Test Setup

Figure 14 Noise Floor at 2 GHz Using HP8662A and Doubler

Figure 17 Absolute Phase Noise Data for Two-Stage DRO

Figure 15 Residual Phase Noise of Dielectric Resonator Used with Single-Stage Amplifier

Figure 18 Absolute Phase Noise Data for Single-Stage DRO